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Features of Tourist Integration Enterprises

Abstract: *Introduction.* The tourism sector is the most globalized sector of the world economy, as it is constantly expanding its activities in the countries of the world, opening up new opportunities for development. Globalization conditions of business development require enterprises in the sphere of tourism to work closely together and to consolidate their activity, to find new ways of cooperation. This is very difficult to achieve in the context of isolated activity, when the enterprise is a closed system, so in the field of tourism to become effective enterprises get open systems, which are forced to create complex business structures, which include enterprises from different fields of activity and different countries of affiliation, which ensures their further development. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the study is to analyze and systematize the forms and directions of integration of tourism and other companies operating in the tourism market in the context of the systematic integration of tourism enterprises in the global space. The research uses such general scientific methods as monographic, system analysis, synthesis, and generalization. *Results.* The article found that the integration of tourism enterprises can be carried out in three directions: integration in the formation of a tourism product; integration in the promotion and sale of the tourism product; integration of financial support for the processes of formation, promotion and sale of the tourism product. In each of the areas of integration, tourist enterprises can choose different forms of organization of their activities, which forms a system of integration of tourist enterprises. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the obtained results is the formation of a system of integration of tourist enterprises, which, unlike the existing ones, allows the tourism industry enterprises, depending on the stage of work with the tourism product (formation; promotion and sale; financial support) to choose the directions and forms of cooperation through specialization, cooperation, concentration. The practical significance of the obtained

results lies in the possibility of their application in the practical activity of domestic enterprises of the tourism industry to increase the efficiency of their activity, increase competitiveness and as one of the possible strategic directions for further development.

Keywords: tourism enterprise, integration, business consolidation, cooperation, tourism product.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The tourist sphere is the most globalized sector of the world economy, as it is constantly expanding its activities around the world, opening up new opportunities for development, due to the specifics of the tourist product. Tourism is becoming an important profitable sector of the economy, a source of foreign exchange earnings, a means of providing employment in many countries. Its tax revenues can strengthen the state budget at different levels of its formation (Olshanska & Melnyk, 2017). Not only the tourism industry plays an important role in the development of national economies of leading developed countries and countries with traditional tourism development, but also makes a significant contribution to the economies of those countries, which have managed to create a competitive tourism industry in modern conditions (Radchenko, 2012).

The main trends of the world market development of tourist services indicate that tourism has become a powerful sector of the world economy. According to the World Tourism Organization, 5% of the world's gross domestic product is generated by this area; 30% of total exports of services are carried out; every 12th workplace on the planet is in tourism; tourism is one of the five leading export items in 80% of the world, tourism is the main source of foreign exchange earnings for 40% of the world (Radchenko, 2012).

Annually, “over 900 million tourist trips are made, at the economic level, the tourism industry produces up to 10% of world gross domestic product, in the field of socio-economic relations, tourism can claim a certain structural level due to the fact that every 15th person in the world is somehow connected with the tourism industry” (Kucherenko, 2013). The number of international tourist trips (overnight stays) worldwide increased by 4% in 2019 and reached 1.5 billion, according to the data reported at destinations all around the world. In 2019, there was a great increase (+ 11%) compared to 2017 (+7%) and 2018 (8%) in the volume of tourist services. During 2019, changes in the structure of tourist services were noticed, world leaders of the tourism market changed, as the results the large travel company Tomasz Kuk and some related airlines in Europe went bankrupt.

Despite such events in the market of tourist services there was an increasing of profits of travel companies. The Middle East (+8%) was the first,

followed by Asia and the Pacific Ocean (+5%). International arrivals in Europe and Africa (both +4%) have increased in line with the world average level, while in America there was an increase by 2%. It is worth noting that along with profits, there was an increase in spending in the tourism market, so France reported the strongest increase in international tourism spending among the top ten markets, while the United States topped the list in absolute rates of growth. Based on current trends, economic prospects and the World Tourism Organization's confidence index, international tourists travelling is projected to grow from 3% to 4% in 2020 (World Tourism Organization, 2020).

Modern processes of globalization, internationalization and informatization, which take place at the international level, contribute to the creation of new types of tourism enterprises, such as:

- international tourism organizations (World Tourism Organization; International World Tourism Association; World Travel and Tourism Council; International Tourism Union; International Tourism Alliance; World Leisure and Recreation Association, etc.);
- international travel alliances;
- global booking systems for tourist services (Global Distribution System);
- tourist clusters (Shatskaya, 2018).

The initiative of internationalization of production in tourism belongs to the world's leading countries, which generate significant tourist flows, because it brings them the most profit (Smal, 2008), namely: the United States, Canada, Germany, France, Japan, China and others. Globalization conditions of business development require close cooperation and consolidated activities, search for new ways of cooperation from enterprises in the field of tourism. To achieve it is very difficult an independent environment, when the company faces many restrictions and high levels of risk, so in the field of tourism to increase the efficiency of enterprises are forced to create complex business structures which include companies from different fields and different countries of affiliation. ensuring their further development.

State study of the problem. A lot of the scientific works of foreign scientists are dedicated to researching of this problem, namely S. Bernazzani (2019), T. Venetis (2018), as well as domestic scientists, including: O. Harbera (2010), A. Kiziun (2013) are devoted to the study of the development of the world market of tourist services. O. Kornienko, V. Zaitseva, (Zaitseva & Kornienko, 2012), N. Kornilova (2014), K. Kucherenko (2013), A. Melnyk, O. Olshanska (Olshanska & Melnyk, 2017), L. Radchenko (2012)), Z. Shatskaya (2018), G. Sigua (2002), I. Smal (2008), A. Tatoryntseva (2007) and many others.

The works of O. Kornienko, K. Kucherenko, L. Radchenko, G. Sigua, I. Smal, V. Zaitseva, are devoted to the problems of world tourism development in the conditions of globalization. Thus, the works of O. Kornienko and V. Zaitseva are focused on the study of the peculiarities of the development of international tourist services as one of the defining components of the world market of services. I. Smal explores the features and problems of international tourism in the context of globalization. K. Kucherenko studies the tendencies of world tourism development in the context of expansion of international economic relations in tourist production, growth of internationalization of factors of tourist production by means of increase of direct and portfolio foreign investments, exchange of knowledge and technologies, removal of migration restrictions, expansion of TNCs. The works of A. Melnyk and O. Olshanska are devoted to the peculiarities of the development of tourist enterprises in the form of clusters at the regional level. O. Harbera deals with certain aspects of the functioning and development of tourism enterprises, researching the problems of franchising in the organization of the tourism business. A. Kiziun, Z. Shatska, A. Tataryntseva, are engaged in the study of the peculiarities of integration and generalization of perspective directions of cooperation of tourist enterprises both at the national and international levels.

Unresolved issues. The last quarter of the XX and the beginning of the XXI century marked the accelerated development of world tourism, which turned it into a global phenomenon in the number of enterprises operating in this field, forms and technologies of recreation. However, despite the global scale, not all companies in this area are efficient and profitable. Nowadays, the biggest problems of world tourism have been due to the closure of borders between countries in connection with the recommendations of governments of many countries to avoid mass events, limit traffic between countries and the associated decline in demand for air travel and inability to travel due to tourism. fight against the epidemic.

After the end of the quarantine, the sphere of tourism will need to be restored, which determines the need to find new effective forms of exit of tourism enterprises from the crisis and prevent bankruptcy. One of such effective ways is to consolidate the activities of tourism enterprises through integration. However, today the peculiarities of the integration of tourism enterprises at different levels of the national and world economy are not sufficiently studied by both domestic and foreign scientists. Need in profound study of research on the choice of areas and forms of integration of tourism enterprises, development of models and indicators to assess their effectiveness.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article is analysis and systematization of forms and directions of enterprises integration, which operates in the tourism market in the context of tourism industry integration in a globalized.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following tasks:

- research of specificity features of the enterprises integration of tourist branch;
- definition of the basic directions of the tourist enterprises integration which are caused by various stages of work with a tourist product;
- generalization of enterprises forms activity organization of tourist branch in the context of integration, taking into account traditional directions of integration, namely: horizontal, vertical, conglomerate and global integration;
- formation of the system of tourist enterprises integration.

The methodological bases of the study are scientific works and publications of leading domestic and foreign scientists and specialists on the functioning, integration and development of tourism enterprises in the context of globalization.

The main task of the methodology of the study is the process of learning and improving the system of principles, methods, rules and norms, which have already been formed in both foreign and domestic business models of tourist enterprises integration and tested over time. The basis of methodological principles (unity, theory and practice, historical approach to the study of the problem, objectivity, comprehensiveness (comprehensive approach), systematicity), methodological requirements for research is made analysis and systematization of forms and directions of enterprises integration of working in tourism market in the context of the tourism industry integration in a globalized. This made it possible to conduct critical research, process analysis and selection of forms and directions of tourist enterprises integration at different levels of the hierarchy of national and world economies; flexibility and adaptability to integration in the theory and practice of economic systems management; strengthening of practical orientation in scientific researches, value of the developed recommendations concerning economic development of the enterprises of tourist sphere; ensuring the validity of scientific forecasting, vision of prospects for the tourist enterprises development in a globalized, particularly the tourism sector; adherence to the logic of judgment and purity in the theoretical and analytical aspects of scientific research.

The most productive is consideration the process of tourist enterprises integration of in terms of a systematic approach, bearing in mind that this

process can occur primarily at different stages of work with a tourist product, namely at the stages: the formation of a tourist product; promotion and sale of a tourist product; financial support of the processes of formation, promotion and sale of the tourist product.

System-structural analysis helps to explore the integrity of tourism enterprises as an object that operates at different levels of the system of tourist enterprises integration in the structure of the tourism market in the context of a globalized space in which each element has a specific functional purpose. This approach allows you to study the different relationships of the components on the whole.

Research methods. The monographic method is used in the article during the study of published scientific works of foreign and domestic scientists on the specifics of enterprises integration in the tourism industry; methods of qualitative analysis and synthesis – to determine the main directions of tourist enterprises integration, which are due to different stages of work with the tourist product. Empirical substantiation of the main conceptual provisions of the peculiarities of the tourism enterprises integration also uses the results of the authors' own research, which are obtained on the basis of economic observations.

Methods of scientific observation, analysis and synthesis, generalization are used to study the forms of organization of the tourism industry in the context of integration by types of traditional areas of integration.

The study is based on a systematic method of understanding the processes and phenomena in their relationship and development, which is used in the development of the system of tourist enterprises integration. The graphic method was used in the construction of the system of tourist enterprises integration.

Research information base. The information base of the study is the materials published in domestic and foreign periodicals and the Internet, as well as data which were obtained by the author in the process of specially organized research and surveys of specialists in the tourism industry of Ukraine.

Special research methods were used, namely: system-structural analysis to study the process of the tourist product formation and the formation of levels of the system of tourist enterprises integration. For this purpose, a sample observation was conducted, as one of the types of non-continuous observation, of tourist enterprises activity of Kyiv and Dnipropetrovsk regions. Based on the generalization of the strengths and weaknesses of the tourist enterprises of these areas, the peculiarities of their functioning are clarified and the opportunities and threats of different areas of integration are identified. The obtained data formed the basis for the development of the system of tourist enterprises integration.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Directions of integration enterprises of the tourist industry

Tourist enterprises integration, as a way to consolidate the business of several enterprises operating in the tourism market, can be done in three ways:

- 1) integration in the formation of the tourist product;
- 2) integration in the promotion and sale of tourist product;
- 3) integration of financial support for the formation, promotion and sale of tourist product.

Each of these areas of integration involves the emergence of cooperation between individual participants in the tourism market, due to the different stages of work with the tourist product. Cooperation of tourist enterprises should be understood as organizational and economic interactions of tourism entities based on trust that has developed in the process of joint activities or as a result of providing third-party guarantees to maximize the needs of consumers of tourist product (Kiziun, 2013).

At the stage of tourist product formation there is cooperation between tour operators and transport enterprises, accommodation facilities, leisure organizations, insurance companies, hotel and restaurant establishments, consulates. Such cooperation allows to form a complex of transport, hotel, excursion, translation, various household, medical, intermediary and other services which are necessary for formation of a certain tourist product.

At the stage of promotion and sale of a tourist product there is cooperation in two directions: between tour operators and travel agents; travel agents and consumers of tourist services (tourists). The tour operator, as a wholesaler, forms a travel product and sells it through retailers – travel agents, with whom was signed an agreement. Travel agent sells a travel product or individual travel services at the prices of tour operators or service providers to individual consumers – tourists.

At the stage of financial support of formation processes, promotion and sale of a tourist product there is cooperation between tour operators and banking institutions, insurance companies. Banking institutions with which a cooperation agreement has been concluded, provide financing at all stages of work with the tourist product and ensure the smooth flow of funds. Insurance companies with which a cooperation agreement has been concluded ensure the safety of a tourist product or certain tourist services to consumers.

3.2. Formation of the system integration of tourist enterprises

For each of the three areas of integration, tourism enterprises can choose different forms of their activities organization, which forms a system of tourist enterprises integration (*Figure 1*). The system of tourist enterprises integration is aimed at selecting and establishing effective relationships between the elements (enterprises) that ensure long-term consolidation (convergence) of the mission and goals of enterprises that are integrated on a voluntary basis.

At the same time, competitive relations between tourism and other enterprises of the industry are replaced by options for cooperation (partnership) on the basis of specialization, cooperation and concentration.

Figure 1. System of tourist enterprises integration

Source: author's development

Newly created integrated enterprises become entrepreneurial structures, which adhere to the principle of self-financing and show a high level of business activity, become more attractive and profitable for investment. Under the business structure we will understand the voluntary statutory or temporary association of several enterprises of different forms and ownership and (if necessary) individual entities (freelancers) into a single integrated complex open system operating in a globalized environment, which is based on a combination of material and intangible interests of participating companies, acts on the basis of the memorandum or articles of association as a legal entity, in order to develop and commercialize innovative products (goods, works, pos Cr) to improve performance and accelerate the integration of business entities that form a structure (Shatska, 2019).

By establishing and developing integration ties in the integration system, tourist enterprises will be able to:

- consolidate and allocate more efficiently financial, productive, human and other resources to create new tourist products, enter new markets, etc.;
- increase the tourist enterprises competitiveness that have consolidated their business into one;
- reduce transaction costs of tourist enterprises;
- reduce the level of external risks of tourist enterprises by creating a more powerful business structure;
- oust from the market unnecessary intermediaries and competitors in the field of tourism;
- increase control over the organization of activities, technological and labor discipline at the enterprise;
- to introduce innovative technologies of tourist product manufacturing and management system of business structure.

To organize joint activities, tourism enterprises can choose different forms of cooperation, namely: specialization, cooperation, concentration.

Specialization is the manufacture and sale of homogeneous products by the enterprise, operation in a narrow market segment. Specialization of enterprises in the tourism market involves the work of:

- tour operators who specialize only in a certain segment of the tourism market or offer tour packages for certain areas, a package of tour services in some tourist centers;
- enterprises that provide related services to ensure tourism activities included in a particular tourist product, namely: transport and airlines, hotels and restaurants, leisure enterprises, insurance companies, consulates, advertising agencies and others.

Specialization, as a direction of integration, should be chosen by widely diversified tourism enterprises, if the refusal of independent activity in a certain direction brings the company less profit than the transfer of these activities to third parties on a voluntary basis.

The formation, promotion and sale of a tourist product on the basis of specialization requires the tour operator to apply an outsourcing strategy, which “involves the transfer of part of the work, individual function or any action to the company or people who specialize in this field” (Tataryntseva, 2007). Outsourcing some of the functions frees the tour operator from the need to organize a new type of activity, reduces costs and reduces the time to market of a new tourist product. For example, the integration of a tour operator with on-line booking systems provides fast booking of hotels around the world.

Cooperation is a long-term voluntary cooperation between individual independent entities for the joint manufacture and sale of products or services. With this type of cooperation, a diversified enterprise can be integrated only in one area, and in others – to remain independent. Cooperation, as a direction of tourist enterprises integration, is appropriate if the implementation of joint activities will increase the efficiency of both enterprises, expand the list of services included in the tourist product, and improve the conditions of its use by consumers.

Cooperation of enterprises in the tourism market can be carried out in such forms as:

1. Horizontal integration, which involves the association and cooperation in the formation, promotion and sale of tourist products of the same type of enterprises that operate at the same level and are competitors, but in different markets. These include:

a) cooperation of sending tour operators and airlines. The sending tour operator (flyer) actively charters planes owned by local airlines. The tour operator, as the organizer of the charter flight has the opportunity not only to pay the cost of the charter in advance, but also to sell the maximum number of tickets or tickets for the booked flight in order to ensure maximum profitability of the flight. Depending on the forms of cooperation of flyers with airlines there are:

– absolute flyers – large tour operators who are the first to purchase the aircraft in full under a charter agreement, that is, under the agreement with the management of the airline and the ground services of the airport to pay in full and fly at their own risk;

– relative flyers – small tour operators, whose sales and market opportunities do not allow them to fully book a charter flight on their own. Based on the possibilities, such small tour operators consolidate their efforts within the

pool – a temporarily created association that exists to achieve a common goal of its members, dividing the cabin of the airliner into blocks of seats. In the future, the tour operator-customer of the block of seats on a charter flight is responsible and risks within the number of seats in the declared pool;

b) the cooperation of tour operators and hotels led to the formation of a new type of hotels – combo hotels. Combo hotels, as a tourist business structure, have rooms of different classes in one building with a more or less wide range of services for different categories of tourists, share amenities or elements of the hotel, such as parking or lobby, gym or meeting room. For example, Inter-Continental Hotels Group (IHG) has created several joint ventures in the United States and Canada using this technology. In Canada, there are Holiday Inn Express and Candlewood Suites hotels in Edmonton, as well as pipeline facilities, including Staybridge Suites and Holiday Inn Express at the University of Saskatoon; a Staybridge Suites and Holiday Inn Express in Niagara on Lake Ontario; and two hatches, Candlewood and the Holiday Inn Express: in the Grand Prairie, Alta, and another in Woon, Ontario (Venetis, 2018).

2. Vertical integration, which involves cooperation between entities in the process of formation and sale of a tourist product (tour operator and agent, tour operator and transport organization, etc.). This form of cooperation helps “the tour operator to gain power over other players in the industry at the stages of formation, promotion and sale of tourist products” (Tataryntseva, 2007).

3. Conglomerate (diagonal) integration through cooperation, which focuses on the enterprises cooperation of different industries in one functional area. For example, Airbnb, which provides room-sharing services and Flipboard, “an online news integrator that collects news and current content that users share on social media and allows you to watch social media-like material” created a joint product called “Trips” (Bernazzani, 2019). It allows Airbnb tourists to connect with hosts of common interest and actually book this experience while traveling.

4. Global integration through cooperation, which involves cooperation in the formation, promotion and sale of tourist products on the world market. These include:

a) creation of strategic alliances, as a union of independent enterprises and the creation of a centralized management body. The purpose of forming strategic alliances in tourism is to create a unified system of formation, promotion and sale of a tourist product by promoting a single brand (co-brand) and the distribution of financial risk among the members of the alliance. The most widespread strategic alliances were in air transport (*Table 1*).

In this case, the same air carrier may be included in several strategic alliances for different purposes. An example of a domestic strategic alliance

is the partnership of Ukrainian airlines AeroSvit and Donbassaero within the Ukrainian Aviation Group. During the year of joint work, the companies managed to optimize the flight schedule, create conditions for attracting more customers, increase traffic and geographically expand markets. The joint route network includes more than 80 international airlines to 32 countries, as well as 11 destinations between the cities of Ukraine. Transportation is carried out on the latest aircraft, including Boeing and Airbus (Krylia, 2008).

Table 1. The largest strategic alliances in international air transport

The name of the alliance	Year of foundation	Head-quarters	Name of merged companies	Joint passenger traffic
Star Alliance	1997	Frankfurt, Germany	Air Canada, Lufthansa, Scandinavian Airlines, Thai Airways International and United Airlines	727.42 million people per year
Oneworld	1998	New York, USA	American Airlines, British Airlines, Canadian Airlines, Cathay Pacific Airways and Qantas Airlines	341 million people per year
SkyTeam	2000	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Aeromexico, Air France, Delta Air Lines and Korean Air	569 million people per year

Source: composed for (Kornilova, 2014)

According to experts, strategic alliances will also become the basis of the strategy of hotel companies in the XXI century (Zaitseva & Korniienko, 2012);

b) cooperation between enterprises in the tourism market on a franchise basis. Franchising as a form of tourism business, involves the creation of a wide network of similar travel agencies with a single brand, adhere to the same conditions, style, methods and forms of selling travel services established by the franchisee under the franchise agreement. For example, one of the largest tour operators, Tui Ukraine, has about 200 franchises, and Gallop Europe has 60 franchises in Ukraine. The company became the first franchise network in Ukraine to take as its basis the production and sale of branded products, introduce clear service standards, and introduce new sales and quality control technologies (Harbera, 2010);

c) creation of transnational corporations, the main purpose of which is to achieve a common goal of formation and sale of tourist products under the conditions of simultaneous joint operation of enterprises of different indust-

ries and countries, pooling their financial capital. In modern conditions, the world's multinational corporations of the tourism industry have moved from competition to the policy of cooperation and implementation of joint projects through the conclusion of global alliances, the formation of network structures (such as hotel chains). Examples of such unions are “global computer systems for booking a wide range of travel goods and services – from air travel, rail travel and package tours, to car rental, hotel reservations or tickets to a football match or concert” (Zaitseva & Korniienko, 2012), which is a global trend in the tourism industry. Today, there are four leading global travel distribution systems in the world market (Global Distribution System): Amadeus, Galileo, Saber and Worldspan, which are called the “golden four”. Together, these systems include about 500,000 terminals installed in hotels around the world, which is about 90% of the market. 10% are occupied by regional reservation systems and systems that are in the process of merging with one of the above (Shatska, 2019).

The tourist enterprises organization of joint activities o in the form of specialization and cooperation can take place only on the basis of partnership, as a voluntary association of several enterprises for joint implementation of the project as a result of which both enterprises do not cease to exist and do not change ownership.

Concentration involves narrowing the range or concentrating production within a single enterprise. The organization of joint activities of tourist enterprises in the form of concentration involves the merger of several enterprises in the tourism industry through mergers and acquisitions. Mergers and acquisitions (in Ukraine, accession) is one of the ways to integrate enterprises that are in difficult business conditions or to terminate their activities, a way to implement the corporate strategy of one of the participants. Acquisitions (or mergers) are the cessation of the existence of only one or more enterprises that join the “core”, which is not reorganized. As a result of the merger, both companies are reorganized and a new business structure is created.

Within the tourism industry, this can be manifested through the use of modern technologies, narrowing the range of tourist products or segments of the tourism market, improving the quality of service. Concentration can be carried out by:

- absolute concentration – increasing the size of a particular enterprise;
- relative concentration – the distribution of the total output of the industry between enterprises of different types and sizes (relative concentration).

Concentration, as a direction of integration of tourist enterprises, is expedient when the enterprises of the branch, which do not work effectively, are forced to narrow the range of tourist products or segments of the tourist market

and unite with more powerful enterprises of the tourist market to prevent bankruptcy. The result of the concentration of enterprises in the tourism industry is the creation of tourism concerns. The most successful tourism concern in the world is TUI AG (Germany), which includes the container shipping divisions Hapag-Lloyd and Europe's largest Anglo-American tour operator TUI Travel (Tataryntseva, 2007).

4. Conclusions

The results of the study allow us to conclude that the problem of business development of enterprises in the field of tourism in today's globalization requires close cooperation and consolidated activities between enterprises in the industry, finding new ways of cooperation. Therefore, to increase the efficiency of enterprises in the field of tourism, they are forced to create complex business structures, which include enterprises from different fields and different countries of affiliation, which increases their competitiveness and ensures further development both at national and global levels.

1. Consolidation of business in the tourism market through the integration of tourist and other enterprises in the industry can occur in three areas: integration in the formation of the tourist product; integration for the promotion and sale of tourist products; integration of financial support for the processes of formation, promotion and sale of tourist products.

2. For each of the three areas of integration, tourist enterprises can choose different forms of organization of their activities, which forms a system of tourist enterprises integration. To organize joint activities in the system of integration, tourist enterprises should use: specialization, cooperation, concentration.

3. Specialization is the manufacture and sale of homogeneous products by the enterprise, operation in a narrow market segment. Specialization, as a direction of integration, should be chosen by widely diversified tourist enterprises, if the refusal of independent activity in a certain direction brings the company less profit than the transfer of these activities to third parties on a voluntary basis.

4. Cooperation is a long-term voluntary cooperation between separate independent entities for the joint manufacture and sale of products or services. Cooperation, as a direction of tourist enterprises integration, is appropriate if the implementation of joint activities will increase the efficiency of both enterprises, expand the list of services included in the tourist product, and improve the conditions of its use by consumers.

5. Concentration, as a direction of tourist enterprises integration, involves a narrowing of the range or concentration of production within a single

enterprise. Concentration is appropriate when companies in the industry that are not working effectively are forced to narrow the range of tourist products or segments of the tourism market and merge with more powerful companies in the tourism market to prevent bankruptcy.

6. The formation, promotion and sale of a tourist product in the form of specialization takes place using outsourcing.

7. Cooperation of tourist enterprises is carried out by:

a) horizontal integration with the cooperation of sending tour operators and airlines and tour operators and hotels;

b) vertical integration through cooperation between entities in the process of formation and sale of a tourist product;

c) conglomerate integration through cooperation of enterprises of different industries in one functional area;

d) global integration in the areas of: strategic alliances creation; cooperation between enterprises on the basis of franchising; creation of transnational tourist corporations.

8. Concentration of tourist enterprises activities involves the merger of several enterprises of the tourism industry through mergers and acquisitions.

9. Despite the existence of various types and forms of integration, the process of selecting and establishing relationships between tourism enterprises is quite complex, the success of which depends primarily on the correct choice of partner with whom to work and the appropriate form of integration.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results is the formation of a system of tourist enterprises integration, which, unlike existing ones, allows tourist enterprises depending on the stage of work with a tourist product (formation; promotion and implementation; financial support) to choose effective areas and forms of cooperation through specialization, cooperation, concentration.

The practical significance of the results obtained. Can be used in the practice of domestic tourism enterprises to increase the efficiency of their activities, increase competitiveness and as one of the possible strategic directions for further development.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction. Prospects for further research in this area include profound study of research in each of the selected areas and forms of tourist enterprises integration, development of models and indicators to assess their effectiveness.

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